

Impact of CSR on Financial Performance: An Empirical Analysis of Indian Banks

HIMANSHU AGARWALL, RABINDRA KUMAR SWAIN AND CHANDRIKA PRASAD DAS

Abstract: The CSR has been one of the best business practices since time immemorial in boosting overall performance of non-banking companies across the globe. Our study examines CSR impact on performance of commercial banks. This study is based on secondary data for a period of 10 years i.e., 2008 – 2018. Top six public sector and six private sector commercial banks based on net worth have been taken for the study. Correlation and panel data regression model have been applied to measure the relationship and impact. The study concluded that CSR practices in public sector banks have a significant relationship with ROA, but cash holding is not significantly associated with CSR practices. However, in private banks CSR has no impact on ROA or cash holding.

Keywords: CSR, Profit after Tax, Cash holding, Loan and deposit ratio, Net Worth

Introduction

CSR helps to enhance the shareholder wealth. There are two major theories known as stakeholder theory and shareholder theory. Stakeholder theory suggests a firm should not satisfy only the owner, but it should satisfy customers, public, suppliers, employees and others who have an interest in the corporation (Freeman & Evan, 1979). These stakeholders would support the firms' operations in maximizing the profits for shareholders owners of the firm (Deng, Kang, & Low, 2013). Shareholder theory suggests that a firm should think only about the owners of a firm.

In 2013, CSR was made mandatory for all corporations, but banks are doing CSR activities voluntarily. In the study, it is proposed to investigate the relationship of corporate social responsibility initiatives with Return on Asset and Cash Holding of Commercial banks.

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Literature Review

Maqbool and Zameer (2017) examined a study on “Corporate social responsibility and financial performance: An empirical analysis of Indian banks”. They focused on study of relationship between CSR and firm’s financial performance. Their study consists of secondary data and those are collected from 28 listed Indian commercial banks in BSE from 2007 -2016. They found CSR have a positive influence on performance of Indian banks. Ofori et. al. (2014) conducted a research on “Corporate social responsibility and financial performance: fact or fiction? A look at Ghanaian banks”. They examined the CSR impact on fiscal performance. For that they have chosen 22 banks and collected both primary and secondary data for the study. They concluded that CSR is positively related to financial performance.

Palmer (2012) did a study on “Corporate Social Responsibility and Financial Performance”. The purpose was to explore and check the relationship of corporate’s social and financial performance. The required data were collected from S&P 500 firms from 2001-2005 and analyzed by using time-series regression. Sales and Gross margin are taken as CFP variable, CSR programs taken as CSP responsible. The thesis concluded that CSP and CFP have a significant positive relationship.

Hassan and Siddiqi (2016) did a study on “The impact of corporate social responsibility on profit and deposit: A study on commercial banks of Bangladesh.” The aim of this paper was to study the relationship between CSR expenditures with profits and deposits. For that, they used panel data of 7 Bangladeshi commercial banks from 2011-2015. They found that CSR expenditure has a neutral relationship with profit and positive relationship with total deposit.

Taskin (2015) conducted a research on “Relationship between CSR and banks’ financial performance: Evidence from Turkey.” The study aimed to analyze the bi-directional relationship among CSR and financial performance. ROE, ROA and NIM are taken as financial performance variables and triple bottom line to measure CSR. For the study 11 Turkish banks have been taken. It is found that CSR has negatively associated with financial performance. Nollet et. al (2015) examined a research paper on “Corporate social responsibility and financial performance: A non-linear dis aggregated approach.” They attempted to investigate the corporate social and financial performance relationship. They had taken ROA, ROC, Excess stock returns as performance indicators and CSR performance which is measured with Bloomberg’s ESG disclosure score. The data collected from S&P stock market index from 2007-2011. The data analyzed with the help of panel regression model. They found CSP have a negative relationship with Return on capital and U-shaped relationship with Return on

Assets. Sandahl (2016) had conducted a research on “CSR & financial performance in banking sector in Scandinavia.” The purpose of the thesis is to examine linkage between CSR with financial performance. The data had collected from five banks from 2011-2015. Regression model used to establish the linkage and found no connection of CSR and financial performance.

Objectives

The objectives of the study are as follows:

- To analyze the impact of CSR on ROA of top six public & six private commercial banks.
- To determine the influence of CSR on cash holding of top six public and six private commercial banks.

Hypotheses

- Ho₁ The Independent variables do not impact the ROA.
- Ho₂ Cash holding is not affected by CSR variables
- Ho₃ ROA is not influenced by CSR variables
- Ho₄ Cash holding is not associated with CSR variables.

Research Methodology

Variables

Our study is focused on twelve Indian Commercial Banks operated in India which consists of six public sector & six private sector banks. The selection of banks has been based on their net worth. The period under study ranges from 2008 to 2018.

Data on CSR, ROA, Cash holding, Size, Leverage, Capital intensity are collected from secondary data sources. The annual reports of the sample banks, RBI circulars on CSR and Priority Sector Lending, various journals, working papers of World Bank and UN, books and websites are used for data collection.

Measurement of CSR

In present study 10 variables have been selected to appraise CSR initiatives of commercial banks.

Measurement of Performance Variables

The dependent variable in this study are ROA and Cash Holding.

- Return on Assets is calculated as ratio of Net-Income to the Total-Assets.
- Cash holding can be defined as cash and cash equivalents.

Table 1: Variables description

Sl.No.	Variables	Explanation
1	Rural Development (RD)	Contribution towards the development of rural areas
2	Priority Sector Lending (PSL)	The proportion of advances made to priority sector including the sub-sector within each category to Adjusted Net Bank Credit (ANBC) or total advances
3	Environment Protection (EP)	Number of activities done to protect and preserve the environment
4	Community Welfare (Including Women Welfare) (CW)	Number of activities done to develop the community with special reference to women empowerment
5	Farmers' Welfare (FW)	Number of activities done for the upliftment of the farmers and to promote the agricultural sector
6	Health Measures (HM)	Number of measures taken to develop and maintain health and sanitation in the society
7	Education (EDU)	Number of activities done to promote education in the society
8	Entrepreneurship Development (ED)	Numbers of activities undertaken so as to develop the domestic entrepreneurial skill
9	Financial Literacy and Credit Counseling (FLCC)	Contribution towards promoting financial literacy
10	New Initiatives related to CSR (NI)	New initiatives undertaken to bring in the real change in the society/environment

Control Variables

To improve the normality and linearity of the variables, the logarithm of size and cash holding have been used.

Panel Data Regression Model

This study is proposed to determine the relationship of CSR with ROA & Cash Holdings. The ROA, and Cash Holding are considered as dependent variables, whereas, CSR initiatives as independent variable. Thus, the following models are developed for the study.

$$Y_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 CSR_{it} + \beta_2 size_{it} + \beta_3 Leverage_{it} + \beta_4 Capital Intensity_{it} + \mu_{it} \quad (1)$$

$$Y_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 CSR_{it} + \beta_2 size_{it} + \beta_3 Leverage_{it} + \beta_4 Capital Intensity_{it} + \mu_{it} \quad (2)$$

Y relates to financial performance, whereas β_0 is intercept, and β_1 are the slope of the independent variables. Here, i represents bank, t represents time series and ϵ_{it} is error term.

Data Analysis: Public Sector Banks

Table No-1: Multicollinearity test

Variables	Vif (Rule of Thumb:10)
CSR	1.016
Size	1.042
Leverage	1.336
Capital Intensity	1.366

Source: Self compiled

From this report it is observed that VIF value of independent variables is less than the rule of thumb i.e. 10. Here there is no multicollinearity between independent variables and all the variables are eligible for running regression equation.

Table 2: Stationarity test (augmented Dickey Fuller)

Variables	probability(significance value)
Roa	0.99
Cash holding	0.81
Csr	0.67
Size	0.58
Leverage	0.07
Capital intensity	0.96

Source: Self Compiled

H_0^1 : Variables has unit root or not stationarity.

H_1^1 : Variables has no unit root or stationarity.

From the above table it is found that all the variables are stationarity as the significance value is more than rule of thumb i.e. 0.05. So, the null hypothesis does not have sufficient evidence to be accepted i.e. variables have no unit root.

Relationship Between ROA & CSR

In this study the nature of data is panel, so panel data analysis has been used. Fixed effects and Random effects model have been performed on the data and Hausman test is used to find out the better fitting model. From the test it is found that model of Random effects is more suitable i.e. Random effects is appropriate.

The r^2 measures the change in dependent variable due to a change in independent variable. Here the dependent variable i.e., ROA is determined to the extent of 49% by the independent variable i.e., CSR and control variables i.e., Size, Leverage and Capital Intensity combinedly.

As per Annexure -1, P value is less than 0.05 i.e., 0.000 at 5% level of significance. So, our null hypothesis i.e., the independent variables do not have any impact on the ROA of Sample public sector banks, is rejected. Hence, it can be inferred that ROA of the banks is significantly influenced by the independent variables.

$$\text{ROA} = 10.60 + 0.20\text{CSR} - 3.74\text{Size} + 0.02\text{Leverage} - 118.37\text{Capital Intensity}$$

Here β_0 is the value of ROA, independent of all other factors or determinants. The value of β_0 is 10.60 w.r.t ROA i.e., irrespective of other factors, the company would have a positive ROA of 10.60. The slope measures the impact of Independent variables towards the respective dependent variable. Here, CSR shows a positive impact of 0.20% on ROA, which means 1 unit change in CSR leads to 0.20 unit change in ROA. Size shows a negative impact of -3.74% on ROA i.e., a unit change in Size gives fall to 3.74 change in ROA. Also, Capital Intensity inversely affects the ROA of public sector banks by 118.37%. Leverage leads to positive contribution by 0.02% towards ROA.

Also, null hypothesis (H_0^1) was that the "The Independent variables do not impact the ROA of the sample public sector banks." As per Annexure 1, P value is 0.006, 0.004, 0.758 and 0.000 w.r.t CSR, Size, Leverage and Capital Intensity, respectively, which is less than 0.05 at 5% level of significance except Leverage. So, there is no evidence to support the null hypothesis and thus, CSR, SIZE and Capital Intensity have a significant impact on ROA of the sample public sector banks.

Relationship between Cash Holding & CSR

Here fixed effects model is appropriate as the non-acceptance of null hypothesis supports the preference of alternative hypothesis i.e. Fixed effects model is appropriate.

In Annexure -2 r^2 measures the proportionate change in dependent variable due to a change in independent variable. Here the Cash holding is determined to the extent of 75% by CSR and control variables i.e., Size, Leverage and Capital Intensity combinedly.

$$\text{Cash Holding} = -30.72 + 0.09 \text{ Csr} + 16.05 \text{ Size} - 0.17 \text{ Leverage} + 18.81 \text{ capital Intensity}$$

Here, value of β_0 is -30.71. It means irrespective of other factors; the company would have a negative cash holding of -30.71. The slope measures the impact of Independent variables towards the respective dependent variable. Here, CSR shows a positive impact of 0.09% on cash holding, which means 1-unit change in CSR leads to 0.09-unit change in cash holding. Size shows a positive impact of 16.05% on cash holding i.e., a unit change in Size gives rise to 16.05 change in Cash Holding. Also, Capital intensity positively contributes to the cash holding of public sector banks by 18.81%. Leverage leads to inverse contribution by 0.17% towards cash holding.

Null hypothesis (H_{0_2}) was that the "Cash holding is not affected by CSR variables of the sample public sector banks. As per Annexure 2, P value is 0.202, 0.000, 0.074 and 0.397 w.r.t CSR, Size, Leverage and Capital intensity, respectively, which is more than 0.05 at 5% level of significance except size. So, there is no evidence to reject the null hypothesis and thus, CSR, Leverage and Capital intensity have no significant impact on the cash holding of the sample public sector commercial banks.

Private Sector Bank

Table 3: Multicollinearity test

Variables	Vif (Rule of Thumb:10)
CSR	1.040
Size	1.145
Leverage	1.033
Capital Intensity	1.144

Source: Self compiled

From the above test it can be inferred that there is no multicollinearity between independent variables since the VIF value of independent variables is less than the rule of thumb i.e. 10, and all the variables are eligible for running regression equation.

Table 4: Stationarity test (Augmented Dickey Fuller)

Variables	Probability(significance Value)
ROA	0.99
Cash holding	0.94
CSR	0.07
Size	0.99
Leverage	0.09
Capital intensity	0.35

Source: Self Compiled

Ho₁: Variables has unit root or not stationarity.

Ho₂: Variables has no unit root or stationarity.

From the Table 4 it is found that all the variables have stationarity as the significance value is more than rule of thumb i.e. 0.05. So, there is no sufficient evidence to accept the null hypothesis i.e. it can be said that variables has no unit root or stationarity.

Relationship Between ROA & CSR

In the study as per the nature of data, panel data analysis has been used. Fixed effects and Random effects model have been performed on the data and Hausman test is used to find out the better fitting model. The result of Hausman test gives no reason to reject the null hypothesis i.e. Random effect is appropriate.

The r^2 quantifies the change in dependent variable w.r.t the change in independent variable. Here the dependent variable i.e., ROA is determined to the extent of 9% by the independent variable i.e., CSR and control variables i.e., Size, Leverage and Capital Intensity combinedly.

As per Annexure -3, P value i.e., 0.220 which is more than 0.05 taking 5% level of significance. So, our null hypothesis i.e., ROA is not influenced by CSR variables of the sample private sector banks, has no sufficient evidence of being rejected.

$$ROA = -0.19 + 0.08CSR + 0.10size - 0.01leverage + 1.72 \text{ capital Intensity}$$

Here β_0 is the value of ROA, independent of all other factors or determinants. The value of β_0 is -0.19 w.r.t ROA i.e., irrespective of other factors, the company would have a negative ROA of -0.19. The slope measures the impact of independent variables towards the respective dependent variable. Here, CSR shows a positive impact of 0.08% on ROA, which means 1-unit change in CSR leads to 0.08-unit change in ROA. Size shows a positive impact of 0.10% on ROA

i.e., a unit change in Size gives rise to 0.10 change in ROA. Also, Capital Intensity positively affects the ROA of public sector banks by 1.72%. Leverage leads to negative contribution by -0.01% towards ROA.

Also, null hypothesis (H_0^3) was that the “ROA is not influenced by CSR variables of the sample private sector banks”. As per Annexure 3, P value is 0.105, 0.046, 0.219 and 0.865 w.r.t CSR, Size, Leverage and Capital intensity, respectively, which is more than 0.05 at 5% level of significance except size. So, there is no evidence to reject the null hypothesis and thus, CSR, Leverage and Capital intensity have no significant impact on the ROA of the sample public sector banks.

Relationship Between Cash Holding & CSR

Here Fixed effects model is appropriate as there is no supportive evidence to support the null hypothesis and the alternative hypothesis is preferred i.e. Fixed effects model is appropriate.

In Annexure 4 r^2 measures the degree of change in dependent variable caused due to a percentage change of independent variable. Here the Cash holding is determined to the extent of 50% by CSR and control variables i.e., Size, Leverage and Capital Intensity combinedly.

Cash Holding = $1.95 + 0.01 \text{ CSR} + 0.70 \text{ Size} - 0.00 \text{ Leverage} + 11.14 \text{ capital Intensity}$

Here, value of $\hat{\alpha}_0$ is 1.95. It means irrespective of other factors; the company would have a negative Cash Holding of 1.95. The slope measures the impact of Independent variables towards the respective dependent variable. Here, CSR shows a positive impact of 0.01% on Cash Holding, which means 1-unit change in CSR leads to 0.01-unit change in Cash Holding. Size shows a positive impact of 0.70% on cash holding i.e., a unit change in Size gives rise to 0.70 change in Cash Holding. Also, Capital Intensity positively contributes to the cash holding of public sector banks by 11.41%. Leverage leads to zero contribution towards Cash Holding.

Null hypothesis (H_0^2) was that the “Cash holding is not associated with CSR variables of the sample private sector banks”. As per Annexure 4, P value is 0.850, 0.000, 0.739 and 0.522 w.r.t CSR, Size, Leverage and Capital Intensity, respectively, which is more than 0.05 at 5% level of significance except size. So, there is no evidence to reject the null hypothesis and thus, CSR, leverage and Capital Intensity have no significant impact on the Cash Holding of the sample public sector banks.

Findings

- ROA is significantly influenced by CSR initiatives of sample public sector banks.
- Cash holding is not affected by CSR initiatives of sample public sector banks.
- ROA is not influenced by CSR initiatives of sample private sector banks.
- Cash holding is not associated with CSR initiatives of sample private sector banks.

Conclusion

This study tries to examine the relationship between CSR initiatives and Return on Asset, cash holdings. It includes Size, Leverage and Capital intensity as control variables. The study investigates twelve commercial banks out of which six public sector and six private sector commercial banks are selected. For the study, secondary data has been collected from financial reports of individual banks. The time 2008 to 2018 considered for the study. In this study researchers have selected ROA and cash holding as dependent variable and CSR as independent variable. Fixed effects model and model of Random effect have been used to find out the effect of CSR initiatives on performance of sample banks. The results show that CSR initiatives have a significant relationship with ROA in public sector banks and cash holding is not influenced by CSR in public sector banks. In private sector banks CSR has no influence towards ROA and cash holding.

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